

Synthesis of Some New Bis (1,2,4-triazol-3-yl) Disulphides, Sulphides and Sulphones as Potential Pesticides

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Manuscript received 30 October 1978, revised 16 March 1979, accepted 4 August 1979

3-Mercapto-4, 5-disubstituted-1, 2, 4-triazoles obtained by interaction of aryloxy-acetic acid hydrazides and aryl isothiocyanates were treated with bromine and thionyl chloride to yield bis-triazolyl disulphides and sulphides, respectively. The latter on oxidation with hydrogen peroxide furnished the corresponding sulphones. Twelve such compounds were compared with 2, 4-D and Dithane M-45 (Manganese ethylene bis dithiocarbamate with zinc ion) for their herbicidal and fungicidal activities, respectively against two weeds, *Agremona mexicana* and *Cyperus rotundus*; and two fungi, *Aspergillus niger* and *Helminthosporium oryzae*.

ALTHOUGH studies¹⁻⁵ on various 1, 2, 4-triazole derivatives have resulted in many potential pesticides, and a variety of disulphides⁶⁻⁸, sulphides^{9,11} and sulphones¹²⁻¹⁵ are known to possess a broad biocidal spectrum, the title compounds seem to have hardly been studied so far. Furthermore, the title compounds incorporate $>N-C-S-$ moiety, the toxophoric importance of which has been well-stressed¹⁶⁻¹⁸ in many pesticides. Keeping above facts in view, the title compounds have been synthesised with the hope that they might be pesticides of choice.

Scheme 1

An outline of synthesis of the compounds reported in this communication is given in Scheme 1. The compounds were characterised by elemental analyses

and ir spectra. The ir spectra of the compounds I-IV exhibited a sharp band in the region 1625-1695 cm^{-1} which was clearly attributable to $\nu C=N$. The compounds I showed a medium band in the range 2500-2600 cm^{-1} due to $\nu S-H$ which was absent in the compounds II-IV. In the ir spectra of the compounds IV two sharp bands appeared in the regions 1300-1350 and 1130-1170 cm^{-1} due to $-SO_2-$ asym. and sym. stretches, respectively. Moreover, all the compounds I-IV exhibited significant bands in the regions that clearly indicated the presence of substituted benzene nucleus.

Out of the twelve screened compounds, the compounds Nos. 6 and 4 (Tables 2 and 3) exhibited herbicidal and fungicidal activities, respectively of the order of 2, 4-D (sodium salt) and *Dithane M-45* (Manganese ethylene bisdithiocarbamate with zinc ion) against two weeds, *A. mexicana* and *C. rotundus*; and two fungi, *A. niger* and *H. oryzae* at 1000 ppm. It is noteworthy that both of these compounds are the representatives of the disulphides (II). In general, the disulphides (II) were more potent than the corresponding sulphides (III) and sulphones (IV).

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer (model 521) in KBr pellets.

3-Mercapto-4, 5-disubstituted-1, 2, 4-triazoles(I) were prepared according to the method of Paul and Basu¹⁹. Thus a mixture of an appropriate aryloxy-acetic acid hydrazide (0.1 mole) and aryl *iso*-thiocyanate (0.1 mole) in 8% aq. NaOH (200 ml) was refluxed for 5-6 hr, cooled and filtered. The filtrate on acidification

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with cold dil. HCl furnished a thick white precipitate which was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol to give the desired product.

*Bis(4, 5-disubstituted-1, 2, 4-triazol-3-yl) disulphides*²⁰(II) 3-mercaptotriazole (I, 0.04 mole) was stirred with bromine (0.04 mole) in ethanol (35 ml), the disulphide at once began to separate which was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol as colourless shining crystals which were quite pure (TLC). The TLC plates coated with silica gel-G were run in CHCl₃-EtOH (90:10, v/v) and for visualisation exposed to iodine.

The molecular weights of the disulphides (II) as determined by the Rast's camphor method were in good agreement with the calculated values.

Bis(4, 5-disubstituted-1, 2, 4-triazol-3-yl) sulphides(III). The mercapto compound I (10.0 g) was treated with thionyl chloride (50 ml) in cold, and the reaction mixture was kept for 2-3 hr at room temperature. Thionyl chloride was distilled off and the residue was washed with sodium carbonate to give the desired product which was recrystallised from ethanol as a white solid.

*Bis(4,5-disubstituted-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl) sulphones*²¹(IV). The bis-triazolyl sulphide (II, 6.0 g) was suspended in glacial acetic acid (150 ml), to this was added hydrogen peroxide (30%, 40 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 1 hr. Upon cooling and pouring the reaction mixture into water, a precipitate was obtained which was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol to furnish the bis-triazolyl sulphone (IV).

TABLE 1—BIS (4, 5-DISUBSTITUTED-1, 2, 4-TRIAZOL-3-YL) DISULPHIDES, SULPHIDES AND SULPHONES (II-IV).

Sl. No.	R	R'	M. P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	N (%)		S (%)		
						Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
Bis (4, 5-Disubstituted-1, 2, 4-Triazol-3-yl) Disulphides (II)										
1	H	<i>o</i> -Methyl	201	71	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	14.0	14.2	10.6	10.8	
2	H	<i>p</i> -Methyl	215	70	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	13.9	14.2	10.7	10.8	
3	<i>o</i> -Chloro	<i>p</i> -Methyl	244 ^d	65	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	12.8	12.7	9.7	9.7	
4	<i>p</i> -Chloro	<i>o</i> -Methyl	198	75	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	12.5	12.7	9.5	9.7	
5	<i>p</i> -Chloro	H	240 ^d	72	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	13.1	13.3	9.9	10.1	
6	2, 4-Dichloro	<i>o</i> -Methyl	228	85	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ Cl ₄ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	11.3	11.5	8.8	8.8	
7	2, 4-Dichloro	H	238-239 ^d	80	C ₉ H ₁₀ Cl ₄ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	11.7	12.0	8.8	9.1	
Bis (4, 5-Disubstituted-1, 2, 4-Triazol-3-yl) Sulphides (III)										
8	H	<i>o</i> -Methyl	144-145	84	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₂ S	15.1	15.0	5.6	5.7	
9	H	<i>p</i> -Methyl	235 ^d	86	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₂ S	14.7	15.0	5.8	5.7	
10	<i>o</i> -Chloro	<i>p</i> -Methyl	231 ^d	89	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₂ S	13.2	13.4	6.3	5.1	
11	<i>p</i> -Chloro	<i>o</i> -Methyl	228 ^d	90	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₂ S	13.4	13.4	4.9	5.1	
12	<i>p</i> -Chloro	H	138	85	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₂ S	13.9	14.0	5.4	5.3	
13	2, 4-Dichloro	<i>o</i> -Methyl	201	80	C ₉ H ₁₂ Cl ₄ N ₆ O ₂ S	11.8	12.0	4.4	4.6	
14	2, 4-Dichloro	H	218-219	79	C ₈ H ₁₀ Cl ₄ N ₆ O ₂ S	12.6	12.5	5.0	4.8	
Bis (4, 5-Disubstituted-1, 2, 4-Triazol-3-yl) Sulphones (IV)										
15	H	<i>o</i> -Methyl	155	68	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₄ S	14.0	14.2	5.6	5.4	
16	H	<i>p</i> -Methyl	173-175 ^d	62	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₄ S	14.0	14.2	5.3	5.4	
17	<i>o</i> -Chloro	<i>p</i> -Methyl	197-200 ^d	75	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₄ S	12.5	12.7	4.8	4.8	
18	<i>p</i> -Chloro	<i>o</i> -Methyl	162	65	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₄ S	12.6	12.7	4.6	4.8	
19	<i>p</i> -Chloro	H	220 ^d	78	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₄ S	13.5	13.3	4.9	5.1	
20	2, 4-Dichloro	<i>o</i> -Methyl	168	72	C ₉ H ₁₂ Cl ₄ N ₆ O ₄ S	11.3	11.5	4.3	4.4	
21	2, 4-Dichloro	H	160	66	C ₈ H ₁₀ Cl ₄ N ₆ O ₄ S	11.8	12.0	4.4	4.6	

d ; Partly melts with decomposition.

The possibility that the compounds IV might be sulphoxides was ruled out, as they did not respond positively to KI, HCl and starch test^{22,23}. When the compounds IV were heated strongly, the gas evolved (SO₂) blackened green Ni(OH)₂ paper confirming their identity as sulphones²⁴.

The bis-triazolyl disulphides (II), sulphides (III) and sulphones (IV) thus prepared are recorded in Table 1 along with their physical and analytical data.

Herbicidal Screening

Herbicidal activity was evaluated by pre-emergence test at three concentrations viz. 1000, 100 and 10 ppm against *Argemone mexicana* and *Cyperus rotundus*. The number of replications in each case was three. Seeds/tubers of the test plants were soaked for 24 hr in the test solutions and then planted. 2,4-D (sodium salt) was also tested under the similar conditions with a view to comparing the results. The percentage inhibitions by various compounds are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—HERBICIDAL SCREENING

Compound Serial as in Table 1	Average Percentage Inhibition					
	Weed- <i>A. mexicana</i> Concentrations used			Weed- <i>C. rotundus</i> Concentrations used		
	1000ppm	100ppm	10ppm	1000ppm	100ppm	10ppm
2	52.6	40.7	18.3	48.3	31.9	15.7
3	75.7	56.3	29.8	72.9	51.8	25.6
4	70.8	53.4	24.7	71.3	55.0	29.8
6	100	65.5	40.2	100	68.3	39.5
9	48.5	35.0	16.7	41.6	24.8	13.8
10	65.8	38.5	14.6	71.8	43.6	23.8
11	68.2	50.3	20.5	65.0	51.0	19.5
13	75.1	42.2	29.4	80.0	45.6	31.7
16	51.3	37.6	16.9	43.6	26.5	14.6
17	67.9	40.8	22.9	72.3	46.4	24.5
18	69.7	51.0	21.3	66.7	53.5	22.8
20	76.3	43.8	32.5	82.4	47.6	42.9
2,4-D (sodium salt) 100	84.6	66.5	100	82.3	61.1	

Fungicidal Screening

Antifungal activity was evaluated by agar-plate technique²⁵ against *A. niger* and *H. oryzae* at concentrations 1000, 100 and 10 ppm. The number of replications in each case was three. A commercial fungicide *Dithane M-45* (Manganese ethylene bisdithiocarbamate with zinc ion) was also tested under similar conditions with a view to comparing the results. The percentage

inhibitions by various compounds are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3—FUNGICIDAL SCREENING

Compound Serial as in Table 1	Average Percentage Inhibition					
	Organism- <i>A. niger</i> Concentrations used			Organism- <i>H. oryzae</i> Concentrations used		
	1000ppm	100ppm	10ppm	1000ppm	100ppm	10ppm
2	68.1	53.4	35.3	72.3	41.4	29.2
3	82.4	46.9	30.6	71.5	55.6	38.7
4	100	76.2	44.4	100	72.3	46.1
6	80.9	44.3	28.5	82.8	61.8	42.6
9	51.4	43.2	26.6	50.0	29.1	9.3
10	73.6	41.2	23.9	66.1	42.7	24.2
11	86.3	51.2	24.3	69.4	47.1	20.3
13	63.6	40.2	19.3	65.2	39.7	17.4
16	58.2	46.4	28.5	54.7	32.8	17.1
17	76.2	45.6	27.5	66.9	76.1	28.8
18	88.0	56.7	34.4	76.2	50.3	32.7
20	68.3	41.7	20.6	78.3	48.7	29.8
Manganese bis dithiocar- bamate with zinc ion (Dithane M-45) A commercial fungicide 100	85.4	72.2	96.1	82.9	68.4	

Results and Discussion

It is evident from the screening data (Tables 2 and 3) that most of the compounds had significant toxicity at 1000 ppm against both the test weeds and fungi but their toxicity decreased markedly on dilution. The compound Nos. 6 (Table 2) and 4 (Table 3) which are representatives of the disulphides (II) possessed the highest herbicidal and fungicidal activities, respectively against both the test weeds and fungi. In general, the disulphides (II) were more potent herbicides and fungicides as compared to the corresponding sulphides (III) and sulphones (IV). This could be expected from their structure (Fig. 1) which has conditions for S-S bond fission apparently analogous to that of thiram (Fig. 2), a common fungicide, for the activity of which it has been suggested²⁶ that it reacts with thiols, the important cellular constituents, and the mechanism of reaction involves S-S bond fission.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

However, the sulphones (IV) were relatively more toxic than their parent sulphides (III) but the difference in their toxicities was of very low order. The toxicity of the compounds (II-IV) varied with the weeds and fungi as well but no generalisation could be made in this regard.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. R. P. Rastogi, Head of the Chemistry Department, University of Gorakhpur, for providing necessary laboratory facilities, and to Sri A. K. Singh, I. I. T., Kanpur, for recording ir and elemental analyses. Thanks are also due to U. G. C., New Delhi, for providing financial assistance to one of them (H. S.) to carry out this work.

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